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The Development of Social Studies Learning Management Guidelines using Community-Based and Project-Based Approaches to Promote Disciplined Behavior and Responsibility for Learning among Primary School Students in Small Schools

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Abstract

This research aimed to develop a social studies instructional model integrating community-based learning (CBL) and project-based learning (PBL) to foster disciplined behavior and learning responsibility among primary school students in small-sized institutions. A one-group pretest-posttest experimental design was employed with Grade 5 students and one teacher from Ban Koh Nok School. Research instruments included a demographic questionnaire, instructional model evaluation form, and satisfaction survey, validated through the Index of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC). Data analysis used descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation). Findings revealed five learning management strategies developed and evaluated as highly appropriate by experts. Both teachers and students expressed high satisfaction, and the model effectively promoted disciplined behavior and learning responsibility. The study suggests that integrating CBL and PBL provides a meaningful, community-responsive approach that strengthens academic skills, civic engagement, and personal accountability.

However, the study's limitation lies in its small sample size and single-site implementation, restricting the generalizability of the findings. Future research should explore the long-term impacts of the CBL-PBL integrated model on student behavior and academic outcomes across diverse educational contexts and larger sample groups. Additionally, there is a need to develop and validate assessment tools specifically designed to measure behavioral growth and social-emotional learning within CBL-PBL frameworks, as well as investigate the integration of digital technologies to enhance project sustainability and student engagement.

Keywords: Social Studies, Community-based, Project-based, Discipline, Responsibility, Small Schools

Introduction

The rapid transformation of modern society driven by technological advancement has significantly influenced how individuals learn, work, and interact. In response, 21st-century education must equip students with essential skills such as critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, and civic responsibility. In Thailand, the National Strategy (2018–2037) emphasizes the need to develop virtuous, disciplined, and responsible citizens who can contribute meaningfully to their communities. Social studies education plays a crucial role in achieving this objective